

Use of Ethnochemistry Teaching Approach and Achievement and Retention of Senior Secondary Students in Standard Mixture Separation Techniques

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of ethnochemistry teaching approach on achievement and retention of senior secondary students in standard mixture separation techniques. A sample of 198 students from six purposively selected secondary schools out of a population of 3,706 Senior Secondary I students from Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria was used for the study. The study adopted non-equivalent quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Separation Techniques Achievement Test (STAT) with the reliability value of 0.84 using Kuder-Richardson (KR-21). Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study revealed that students taught mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach had significantly higher mean achievement scores than those taught using discussion method [$F(1,197)=405.07, P<0.05$] and students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach had significantly higher mean retention scores than those taught using discussion method [$F(1,197)=293.00, P<0.05$]. It was recommended that chemistry teachers' trainee should be trained on the use of ethnochemistry approach and serving teachers should be encouraged to use ethnochemistry.

Key words: Ethnochemistry, achievement, retention, standard mixture separation techniques.

Introduction

Chemistry is the scientific study of the composition, structure, properties, and reactions of matter. The importance and value of chemistry in the social and economic sphere of any nation is immense and, Nigeria is not an exception. Chemistry is a broad scientific subject and its relevance is seen in almost every aspect of society including medicine, food security and agriculture, science and technology, cooking, and environmental issues. Chemistry enables students to understand what happens in the world they live in and how it contributes to the quality of life on our planet (Ware, 2001). Due to its importance, the teaching of chemistry should be done in such a manner that students would have deep understanding for it.

However, research shows that chemistry is generally a difficult subject to students at all levels (O'dwyr, 2012). This is also reflected in the achievement of students in chemistry external examinations such West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO). Low achievement of students in chemistry could also be ascribed to the use of non-innovative and activity-based strategies but rather regular use of conventional teaching method such as lecture, demonstration and discussion methods that does not put into consideration the students' culture, background, and experience in teaching and learning processes. For decade now, teachers, parents, government and the general public have been perplexed and

disturbed immensely by the poor achievement of students in chemistry (Olorundare, 2014). This is because chemistry introduced in our system is foreign and euro-centric in origin, and built on western cultural background and it has no meaning to students because it seems unreal. Therefore, they resorted to learning by rote memorization, which resulted in consistent poor achievement.

Foreign or euro-centric nature of chemistry invariably translates to students' poor achievement and inability to retain what is learnt in classroom. However, there have been ongoing endeavours to explore and implement several possible interventions to improve students' achievement and retention in Chemistry. One of such interventions is to teach the subject beginning from what the student already knows. This brings about meaningful learning (Gregory & Mayer, 2002). The inclusion of knowledge related to ethnochemistry practices may instill a sense of ownership about the concept and to improve achievement and retention of students in chemistry.

Ethno encompasses identifiable cultural groups such as national tribal societies, labour groups, ideologies, daily practices and specific way of reasoning and inferring. In other words, ethno refers to members of a group within a cultural environment identified by their cultural traditions, codes, symbols, myths, and specific ways used to reason and to infer. For instance, when defining ethnomathematics, D'Ambrosio cited in Rosa and Orey (2011) defined the prefix ethno as a very broad term that refers to the social-cultural context and therefore includes language, jargon, and codes of behaviour, myths, and symbols.

Indra and Bitwell (2016) opine that ethnochemistry are the various chemically related cultural and community practices. It describes the chemical practices of identifiable cultural groups and may be regarded as the study of chemical ideas found in any

culture. In this regard, ethnochemistry may help to sequence teaching/learning processes through previous knowledge of the culture, so as to offer the opportunity for learners to know more about reality, culture, society and themselves. By implication, the approach may encourage students to see and think chemistry within themselves and to arrive at a meaningful learning and understanding towards proper application for improved achievement and retention.

Ethnochemistry is the study of chemistry practices of specific cultural groups in the course of dealing with their environmental problems and activities using their own ideologies. In this regard, ethnochemistry teaching approach can be describe as a means of organizing chemistry instruction based on diverse cultural context. Ethnochemistry approach to chemistry curriculum is an approach that draws on traditional culture while focusing attention on the chemistry needed by the learners in an integrated society. In other words, ethnochemistry teaching approach is an approach adopted by the teacher in the process of teaching chemistry through the use of learners' culture, background, in understanding, explaining and managing situations and activities arising in their own environment.

In this regard, the aim of ethnochemistry approach in this study is to use already existing familiar mixture separation techniques activities in the learners' culture, environment, background, reasoning and experiences, integrated with foreign-centric standard mixture separation techniques to help them develop skills to improve their level of standard mixture separation techniques functioning in a wide range of standard mixture separation techniques objective as well as to improve their achievement and retention in such concept. According to Kurumeh and Opara (2008) ethno method of teaching involves situating learning and

problem solving in real life context where the environment is very rich in information with physical materials that serve as a source of manipulative and interactive processes; Students are made to link the past to the present so as to build the future; The teacher then explores the cultural experiences of the learners based on the initial experiences to teach the present school (academic) and relate to their environmental usefulness.

Many students and teachers experience chemistry as a rather strange subject, imported from outside Africa (Indra & Bitwell, 2016). In order to overcome this psychological and cultural blockage to the learning and development of chemistry, ethnochemistry practices may be incorporated into chemistry lessons in order to improve students' achievement and retention in chemistry. Incorporating ethnochemistry in chemistry instructions may enable students to veal chemistry as a familiar subject, and not one that is strange imported from outside Africa. Indeed, these indigenous chemically related practices may be used to make the unfamiliar chemistry content familiar to students. For instants, mixture separation phases of brine in traditional production of table salt (sodium chloride) may be used when teaching standard mixture separation techniques such as filtration, decantation,. Furthermore, the traditional practice of blacksmithing can be used when teaching extraction of iron in the blast furnace. This study intends to employ the reach cultural environment of the study area especially their traditional salt production activities to teach standard mixture separation techniques in chemistry.

Standard mixture separation techniques is a scientific process or method to achieve any phenomenon that converts a mixture of chemical substance into two or more distinct product mixtures, which may be referred to as mixture, at least one of which is enriched in one or more of the mixture's constituents (Wilson, & Adlard, 2005). The

authors further explain that, in some cases, a separation may fully divide the mixture into its pure constituents. Separations are carried out based on difference in chemical properties such as size, shape, mass, or chemical affinity between the constituents of a mixture, and are often classified according to the particular differences they use to achieve separation. Mustafa (2015) explains that, the method used to separate mixtures depends upon the type of mixture. The author further outlines types of standard mixture separation techniques as extraction, filtration, decantation, evaporation, sublimation, simple and fractional distillation, crystallization, chromatography among other.

It is one thing to be taught standard mixture separation techniques via appropriate approach; it is another thing to remember it after some reasonable period of time must have elapsed that is retention. Retention as defined by Hornby (2001) is the ability to remember things within a specific time. For the purpose of this study, retention is defined as the ability to keep or retain the knowledge of standard mixture separation techniques learnt and to be able to recall it when required. Retention in chemistry is not acquired by mere rote-memorization but through appropriate teaching method. Adepoju cited in Ogbeba and Ajayi (2016) opine that retention is measure in collaboration with achievement. This implies that achievement is a function of retention. In this regard, the researcher sees the need to find out if ethnochemistry approach could improve retention of students in standard mixture separation techniques.

The study incorporated the ethnochemistry knowledge relevant to different types or methods of standard mixture separation techniques concepts such as filtration, distillation, evaporation, extraction and sedimentation/decantation in chemistry lessons. In this regard, the study examined effect of ethnochemistry teaching approach on achievement and retention of senior secondary students in standard mixture separation

techniques in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State as a study area. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to;

1. determine the effect of ethnochemistry teaching approach on students' achievement in standard mixture separation techniques
2. ascertain the effect of ethnochemistry teaching approach on students' retention in standard mixture separation techniques

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean retention scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught using discussion method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught using discussion method.
2. The difference in the mean retention scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught using discussion method is not significant.

Ethnochemistry and its Practical Application in Ebonyi State, Nigeria

Viewed from all perspectives ethnochemistry is rooted from ethnoscience. According to Atran (1991) ethnoscience looks at culture with a scientific perspective. The scholar further added that, ethnoscience refers to knowledge that is indigenous to a particular culture. Ethnoscience is concerned with natural objects and events that may have potentially the same branches as the western science, in which case therefore, one may speak of ethnophysics, ethnobiology, ethnochemistry, ethnozoology, ethnomedicine and so on. As earlier remarked, ethnochemistry teaching approach is describe as a means of organizing chemistry instruction based on diverse cultural context. In the present study, traditional or ethno knowledge of salt making process relevant to standard mixture separation techniques concepts such as extraction filtration, sedimentation, decantation and evaporation in chemistry lessons are particularly employed

Ebonyi State is the second largest small-scale salt producing areas in Nigeria. The small-scale salt production in Uburu and Okposi Okwu districts in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State has continued for over 40 decades (Okaji, 2009). Uburu and Okposi Okwu people in Ebonyi State are very rich in culture and tradition. The traditional occupation of the Uburu and Okposi Okwu people is salt production. According to Anyim (2012) salt or table salt, is a crystalline mineral that is primarily composed of sodium chloride (NaCl). It is essential for animal life in small quantities, but is harmful to animals and plants in excess. Salt is one of the oldest, most ubiquitous food seasonings and salting is an important method of food preservation. Like all other people in the world, Uburu and Okposi Okwu people have their indigenous and native process or method with which they carry out their day to day salt production activities. Meanwhile,

scientifically, salt making process from brine involves series of mixture separation phrases.

As earlier remarked, the main occupation of Uburu and Okposi Okwu people is salt production. Therefore, their traditional mixture separation technique practices evolved in their quest to produce salt from the brine (Brine is water containing a high concentration of salt). The people of Ebonyi State of Nigeria especially Uburu and Okposi Okwu people in Ohaozara Local Government Area mainly have very rich cultural practices that could be used to advantage to teach standard mixture separation techniques in Chemistry. Consequently, how they produce their salt is interesting. It is to be noted that no matter how crude the method, salt preparation is not a craft but a scientific process. In this regard, salt making process from brine scientifically involves series of standard mixture separation phrases such as extraction, filtration, decantation, evaporation, sublimation, among other phases.

Let us consider their traditional salt production process. The people especially women begin salt production by securing a piece of land (salt plot) and leveling it, after which they provides big earthen pots which may be six or more depending on their ability. The pots are arranged in a straight line and supported with big stones, which raise the pots completely from the ground. With wet clay soil, the stones are held together and in place. These large pots in a line are called by Uburu people "Ofufu" (Ofufu is a pot perforated at the base) behind the "Ofufu" is mounted another pot larger than Ofufu. The larger pot is called "Onini" which have a different function from "Ofufu". The larger pot behind the Ofufu is meant for storing brine to be used in Ofufu when necessary.

The actual salt production starts with the collection of 'salty earth' from the water-bed of the lake using a flat metal called "atakpa" (that process is, extraction: a separation technique used to separate a desired

substance from a natural source). Thereafter, the big pots (ofufu) are filled with earth until it gets to the brim. The water and the earth in the big pots (ofufu) are allowed to knead properly by leaving them over night with the small perforations at the bottom of the Ofufu still blocked. In the morning, the perforations at the bottom of the Ofufu are opened (irufu eja) to allow the filtrate to drain into the earthen conical dish beneath the "Ofufu-nja ugbani" (that process is, filtration: a separation technique used to separate heterogeneous mixtures composed of solids and liquids. The technique uses a porous barrier to separate the solid from the liquid). Sometimes they use "alom" to effect sedimentation of dirt before pouring off the upper liquid layer (that process is, decantation: is a separation technique used to separate a liquid from an insoluble solid). Then the filtrate in the "nja ugbani" is collected and taken home for boiling to get salt (that process is evaporation: in this separation method, the mixture is heated, when the mixture has completely evaporated, no water is left behind, the solid salt is left behind as the residue).

Research Design and Procedures

The study used pre-test, post-test non-equivalent quasi experimental design. The pre-test score constituted the covariant of the post-test scores. In order to find out if the knowledge gained was retained, the post-test was reshuffled and administered as retention test to measure the subjects on retention. One regular chemistry teachers from each of these six schools were used to teach the students. These research assistants were trained by the researchers for one week before the commencement of the study. The training exercise was based on the purpose of the study, the topic to be taught, the use of the lesson plans, the use of the Separation Techniques Achievement Test (STAT) as well

as general conduct of the study. These teachers were trained to teach both the experimental and control groups. The experimental groups were taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach in line with lessons procedure prepared by the researcher while the control group was taught standard mixture separation techniques using the discussion lesson notes.

The study was carried out in Ohaozara Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria. Districts under Ohaozara Local Government Area includes: Uburu, Okoposi (Okoposi Okwu), Ugwu-Langwu, Akaeze and Ishiagu districts. The population of the study comprised all the 3,706 SSI students in the 37 government approved secondary schools. 198 students were purposively sampled from 6 schools that had some basic facilities and equipment in their laboratories. One instrument known as Separation Techniques Achievement Test (STAT) was used to collect data for this study. STAT was validated by three experts of Science

Education/Measurement and Evaluation from Benue State University, Makurdi. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument before it was used.

STAT is a researcher made instrument that contains two sections. Section A contains bio-data information of the respondents, while section B contains 30 multi-choice objective items questions to which respondents were expected to provide the answer by selecting the correct option (A-D). Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) was used to obtain the STAT reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.84.

Results and Table

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and hypotheses:

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question one is contained on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Achievement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Standard Mixture Separation Techniques using Ethnochemistry Approach and Discussion Method

Group	N	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Ethnochemistry	98	13.67	1.26	30.43	1.66	16.76
Discussion	100	13.65	1.24	17.35	1.47	3.70
Mean difference		0.02		13.08		13.06

Table 1 revealed that, the overall mean difference between the two groups was 13.06 in favour of the ethnochemistry approach group. It implies that the ethnochemistry

approach group achieved higher than the discussion method group counterpart.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean retention scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry

approach and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question two is presented on Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Retention and Standard Deviation Scores of Students taught Standard Mixture Separation Techniques using Ethnochemistry Approach and Discussion Method

Group	N	PRE-TEST		RETENTION-TEST		Mean Gain
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Ethnochemistry	98	13.67	1.26	31.04	1.72	17.37
Discussion	100	13.65	1.24	16.22	1.38	2.57
Mean difference		0.02		14.82		14.80

The results on Table 2 revealed that, the overall mean difference between the two groups was 14.80 in favour of the ethnochemistry approach group. It implies that students taught using ethnochemistry had higher retention capacity than those exposed to discussion method.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught using discussion method. The answer to hypothesis one is presented on Table 3.

Table 3: ANCOVA Result for Mean Achievement Scores of Students taught Standard Mixture Separation Techniques using Ethnochemistry Approach and Discussion Method

Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected model	1908.101a	2	422.009	195.021	.000
Intercept	1520.020	1	1520.020	272.972	.000
Pre-test	206.009	1	206.009	94.034	.000
Method	1590.925	1	1590.925	405.070	.000
Error	409.397	195	7.980		
Total	100998.099	198			
Corrected Total	3708.490	197			

a. R squared = .174 (Adjusted R Squared= .131)

ANCOVA result on Table 3 reveals that there is a significant difference between ethnochemistry approach and discussion method of teaching [F(1,197)=405.07, P<0.05]. The null hypothesis therefore rejected. This implies that ethnochemistry approach is significantly more effective than

discussion method in achievement of students in standard mixture separation techniques.

Hypothesis Two

The difference in the mean retention scores between students taught standard mixture separation techniques using

ethnochemistry approach and those significant. The answer to hypothesis two is taught using discussion method is not presented on Table 4.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result for Mean Retention Scores of Students taught Standard Mixture Separation Techniques using Ethnochemistry Approach and Discussion Method.

Source	Type III sum of square		Mean Square	<i>F</i>	Sig
Corrected model	2690.312a	2	355.093	235.029	.000
Intercept	1992.200	1	1992.200	502.001	.000
Pre-test	227.309	1	227.309	86.888	.000
Method	1996.028	1	1996.028	293.003	.000
Error	490.320	195	11.310		
Total	219903.000	198			
Corrected Total	1209.791	197			

a. R squared = .676 (Adjusted R Squared= .603)

ANCOVA result on Table 4 reveals that there is significant difference in the mean retention scores between the students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach and those taught with discussion method [$F(1,197)=293.00$, $P<0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that ethnochemistry approach significantly enhanced students' retention in standard mixture separation techniques than discussion method.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that students taught standard mixture separation techniques using ethnochemistry approach achieved higher than their counterparts taught using discussion method. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that ethnochemistry approach helped the learners to integrate or link their cultural background of the study and their immediate environment with the foreign aspect of the learning of standard mixture separation techniques when compared to discussion method. This finding agrees with Indra and Bitwell (2016) who reported that incorporating ethnochemistry practices in teaching chemistry enhanced significantly secondary school students' attitude towards chemistry. The finding is also in agreement with Achor, Imoko and Uloko (2009) who reported that students exposed to ethnomathematics teaching approach were superior in achievement and retention than those exposed to conventional teaching method. Generally speaking, this implies that ethnoscience is rewarding in term of students' attitude, achievement and retention in most science subjects.

It was also found that students exposed to ethnochemistry approach had higher retention capacity than those exposed to discussion method. The reason for this

higher retention by students taught using ethnochemistry approach could be that they were able to reflect on, interpret and search for solutions to problems through their reflective observations of culture practices when compared to students taught using discussion group. In this regard, students' abilities to reflect on their cultural practices may have the tendency of enhancing their retention capacities. The finding agrees with Ann (2012) who found that students have higher retention capacity when they are allowed link their already existing culture knowledge in solving problems through cultural learning style than when they become passive learners as obtained in the use of traditional method.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of ethnochemistry teaching approach enhanced students' achievement and retention in standard mixture separation techniques than the use of discussion method. Based on the conclusion, it is recommended that: Chemistry teacher's trainee should be trained on the application of ethnochemistry. Serving teachers should employ the use of ethnochemistry teaching approach to enhance students' achievement and retention in standard mixture separation techniques. Ministry of Education and professional bodies such as Association of Science Educators (ASE) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize conferences or seminars and workshops to popularize and sensitize chemistry teachers on the integration of ethnochemistry knowledge in teaching chemistry concepts, also chemistry curriculum should be restructured to reflect Nigerian culture (indigenous chemistry practices).

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